

STUDENTS' PREFERRED LEARNING MODALITIES AND THEIR LEARNING STYLES: BASIS FOR DIFFERENTIATED INSTRUCTION MODEL

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ABSTRACT

This study is intended to determine the relationship between the students' learning styles and their preferred learning modalities in mathematics in the new normal in terms of face-to-face classes, online classes, and blended learning and examine how it relates to their academic performance. A quantitative descriptive research design was implemented in this study. The respondents were two hundred thirty – three (233) junior high school students from selected private schools in Dinalupihan, Bataan S.Y. 2022 – 2023. To fulfill the objectives of the study, the researcher used a combination of standardized math learning style inventory and a researcher-made questionnaire to gather data, which has a Cronbach's alpha of 0.771. The data reveals that most of the students are visual learners, and their preferred learning modality is face-to-face class in the new normal. Results further showed a significant difference between the students' preferred learning modalities when they were classified according to learning styles. Furthermore, a path analysis is used to show the significant relationship between the students' learning styles and their preferred learning modalities in relation to their academic performance in mathematics. Based on the path analysis, an Identify, Design, Implement, and Assess (IDIA) model was developed in planning differentiated instruction for the teachers.

Keywords: *Learning Modalities, Learning Styles, Differentiated Instruction Model, Path Analysis*

INTRODUCTION

Mathematics is a challenging subject for students to learn. Every student learns mathematics in a unique manner. Given the socio-educational difficulties posed by COVID-19, the pandemic has changed the mode of instructional delivery of the teaching-learning process. It also altered the viewpoint of the education stakeholders on the kind of continuity applicable to the learners amidst the looming uncertainty brought on by the pandemic.

Learning in the new normal is challenging for teachers, students, parents, and guardians. In order to respond to the educational needs of students during the pandemic, education must continue as required by the Department of Education. The DepEd developed the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) to make sure that our children have access to a range of safe learning alternatives, including learning modules, distance learning, blended learning, and hybrid learning (DO 18, s. 2020).

Digital tools facilitate communication between teachers and students while also offering new opportunities for differentiated learning that many teachers had not foreseen. Classrooms have started to integrate online platforms and activities that can be customized to meet each student's needs. Thus, differentiated instruction and student engagement are essential to achieving learning objectives in the online learning environment (Ferlazzo, 2021).

According to Anthonysamy (2020), a student's performance is positively influenced by his or her level of digital literacy. While using online resources, specifically social media, students also improve their digital literacy skills and cognitive capacities, which are necessary to filter out important information (Tinmaz et al., 2023). Furthermore, digital literacy encompasses the ability to understand points of view, critical thinking abilities for analyzing and evaluating the trustworthiness of information, expertise in accessing various types of information, and exposure to digital settings.

Nonetheless, a significant challenge lies in determining how users can effectively use technology while maintaining participants' commitment, considering their unique learning styles and technological experiences. Students who have difficulties with technology may discontinue their studies, resulting in unsuccessful technology applications (Hofmann, 2014).

In the teaching-learning process, teachers need to remain flexible in assessing suitable techniques for their students, regardless of whether the learning environment is blended. However, the challenge lies in the need for teachers to allocate additional time to research different strategies to support students. As a result, many sessions must be both meticulously prepared and adaptable at the start of the class (Onyishi, 2022).

While much has been written about the rapid shift to distance learning during COVID-19, there remains a significant gap in understanding how this transition has influenced the long-term effectiveness and sustainability of educational practices. Most

existing studies primarily focus on the immediate challenges faced by teachers and students, such as technological access, learning engagement, and adaptation to online platforms. However, limited research has examined how the ongoing evolution of hybrid and digital learning environments has reshaped pedagogical approaches, student learning outcomes, and the role of social interaction in the learning process in the "new normal".

Thus, the study aims to determine and investigate the relationship between the students' preferred learning modalities and their learning modalities in the new normal towards their academic performance in mathematics at five selected private schools in Dinalupihan, Bataan. By investigating these dynamics, the research contributes to a deeper understanding of how the new normal in education may influence learning outcomes, teacher-student interactions, and the role of technology in shaping educational practices for years to come.

Theoretical Framework

The study is anchored on three theories, which are the following: the Visual, Auditory, and Kinesthetic (VAK) Learning Theory by Walter Buke Barbe (1970), the Theory of Cognitive Learning by Jean Piaget (1972), and the Constructivist Theory by Jerome Bruner (1966).

The Visual, Auditory, and Kinesthetic (VAK) Learning Theory, developed by Walter Buke Barbe, proposes that individuals possess unique preferences for the absorption and processing of information. It categorizes these preferences into three main learning modalities: Visual, Auditory, and Kinesthetic. The theory proposes that by recognizing and addressing these preferences, educators can enhance learning results by employing strategies that align each student's preferred learning style.

This theory is connected to the present study because it plays a significant role in developing teaching methods and strategies that cater to the various learning styles of students. By identifying that student have different ways of learning, teachers can adjust and select appropriate teaching methods to enhance and increase student engagement and learning retention. This approach fosters a more inclusive learning environment, where students are better prepared to grasp and retain the content, resulting in effective educational outcomes. Therefore, the VAK theory supports the concept of differentiated instruction.

The Cognitive Learning Theory by Jean Piaget is a framework that stresses the learners' schema as a systematized knowledge structure intended to interpret information. Jean Piaget coined the term "schema," which has become widely used in psychology. In his point of view, a schema can be defined as both a category of information and the process of knowledge accumulation. Piaget explains that children's cognitive development progresses through a succession of phases of intellectual growth. Moreover, as the experiences happen, new information will be acquired, new schemas will develop and form, and previous schemas will alter over time.

This theory is related to the present study since the learning modalities will help the teachers deliver the lesson to the students in the new normal. Students have a schema or prior knowledge of the different lessons in mathematics since the mathematics curriculum, which the Department of Education implements, is spiral. Thus, the students can use their prior knowledge to acquire and understand the lessons in order to create new information.

Bruner's Constructivist Theory regards knowledge as an established unit composed of all learnings. Constructivism is a theory that views learning as the result of passive transmission rather than an active development process in which learners create new knowledge based on previous experience and knowledge. Furthermore, this theoretical perspective holds the assumption that it involves an active process of developing concepts and shaping new types of information through engagement. Thus, constructivist learning theory explains that the best way to get new knowledge is by taking action, reflecting, and constructing.

As explained by Bruner, students can construct their knowledge through their existing schemas and past experiences. Generally, it is aligned with the present study since it is more on learner-centered instruction where the students can process and acquire new knowledge through the assistance and guidance of the teacher, whatever of the learning modalities that the teacher utilized.

VAK, Cognitive, and Constructivist theories are relevant to the present study since learning is most effective when it caters to individual preferences (VAK), actively engages learners in meaningful experiences (Constructivism), and supports the mental processes needed to understand and create new information (Cognitive Theory).

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

The study explores the relationship between students' learning styles and their preferred learning modalities in relation to their academic performance in mathematics. The profiles of the respondents are included to determine the face-to-face classes, online classes, and blended learning and to analyze their relationship to their academic performance in mathematics.

The study is limited only to the junior high school students from five private schools in Dinalupihan, Bataan, namely College of Subic Montessori – Bataan, Eastwood College of Science and Technology, Mother Margherita de Brincat Catholic School Inc., St. John's Academy, and University of Nueva Caceres – Bataan of the School Year 2022 – 2023, from first to third quarter.

Research Questions

The general problem of the study is to determine how the students' preferred learning modalities and their learning styles relate to their academic performance in

mathematics among junior high school students at five selected private schools in Dinalupihan, Bataan, during the school year 2022 – 2023.

Specifically, the study investigates the following:

1. What is the learning style of the students in terms of:
 - 1.1 visual
 - 1.2 auditory, and
 - 1.3 kinesthetic?
2. How may the students' preference in learning modalities be described in terms of:
 - 2.1 face-to-face classes,
 - 2.2 online classes, and
 - 2.3 blended learning?
3. How may the academic performance of the students in mathematics be described in terms of their grade point average?
4. Is there a significant difference in the students' preferred learning modalities when they are classified according to learning style?
5. Based on the findings of the study, what differentiated instruction model can be derived from the path analysis of students' learning styles and preferred learning modalities to their academic performance in mathematics?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The researcher used a quantitative descriptive research design to determine how the students' preferred learning modalities and their learning styles relate to their academic performance in Mathematics in the new normal.

According to Siedlecki (2020), descriptive research design is a quantitative method that is described as the collection of numerical data for the statistical analysis of a sample data set in a population. Moreover, a descriptive survey examines population characteristics, identifies conflicts within an entity, a population, or an organization, and examines differences in behaviors and characteristics between institutions.

Zulueta and Costales (2003) considered a descriptive type of research as a method of study that concentrates on the present situation with the purpose of finding the new truth and may take various forms, such as expanded knowledge, a generalization of a new law, insight into the elements influencing the discovery of a new causal relationship, or a more precise statement of the problem to be addressed.

Furthermore, Creswell (2012) described that survey research designs are quantitative research methods in which the researcher conducts a survey of sample participants or the complete population to describe their characteristics. Likewise,

descriptive research deals with how what is or what is current relates to a previous event that influenced or affected a current state.

Population and Sample of the Study

The respondents of the study are randomly selected junior high school students of the private schools in Dinalupihan, Bataan, namely College of Subic Montessori, Eastwood College of Science and Technology, Mother Margherita de Brincat Catholic School, St. John's Academy, and University of Nueva Caceres – Bataan.

Table 1. Population and Samples of the Study

Name of School	Population	Sample	Percentage
CSM	106	37	35.85%
ECST	64	29	45.31%
MMDBCS	329	53	16.11%
SJA	803	69	8.59%
UNC	267	45	16.85%
Total	1569	233	100%

As presented in the table, there were one thousand five hundred sixty-nine (1,569) students from the five selected private schools in Dinalupihan, Bataan. Based on the population, the researcher used cluster random sampling to identify the respondents who were interested and willing to participate in answering the questionnaires. In this sampling technique, respondents are chosen randomly in each grade level, and it will serve as the representative of their population. The accumulated sample size in the study is two hundred thirty-three students. Out of these 233 respondents, thirty-seven (37) from CSM, twenty-nine (29) from EWCST, fifty-three (53) from MMDBCS, sixty-nine (69) from SJA, and forty-five (45) from UNC.

Research Instrument

The researcher used survey questionnaires as the main instrument to gather data. The questionnaire is composed of three parts.

The first part of the questionnaire is an adapted set of questions to assess the dominant learning styles of the students in mathematics. The second part is a set of questions about the students' preferred learning modalities in the new normal. Lastly, the third part is used to obtain the average grade of students in mathematics from the first to third quarter.

The assessment of the learning styles of the students in mathematics was adapted from Arem (2009), and it is composed of 30-item questions. The items used to determine

the students' preferred learning modalities in mathematics in the new normal are a researcher-made questionnaire.

The set of questions evaluating the students' perception of the learning modalities in the new normal is evaluated and measured by the 5-point scale.

5	–	Strongly Agree
4	–	Agree
3	–	Neutral
2	–	Disagree
1	–	Strongly Disagree

To describe the students' academic performance in Mathematics in terms of their grade point average, is a scale based on the implemented by the DepEd Order No. 8, s. 2015.

Grading Scale	Description
90 – 100	Outstanding
85 – 89	Very Satisfactory
80 – 84	Satisfactory
75 – 79	Fairly Satisfactory
74 and below	Did not Meet Expectations

Construction and Validation of Instrument

The survey questionnaire is composed of three parts. The first part of the questionnaire assesses the dominant learning style of the students in mathematics; the second part is a set of questions to determine the students' perspective on the different learning modalities in mathematics in the new normal. Lastly, the third part aims to attain the average grade of the students in mathematics from the first to the third quarter.

Specifically, the set of questions for assessing the students' learning styles consists of 30 items adapted from Math Specific Learning Style Preferences by Arem (2009). The set of questions to evaluate the students' preferred learning modalities in mathematics in the new normal is the researcher's questionnaire.

Since the set of questions contained in the questionnaire is a combination of adapted and researcher questionnaires, the researcher first sought permission from the author for the adapted questionnaire. The researcher validated the questionnaire by asking the research adviser to check the instrument. Furthermore, the researcher asked the other mathematics instructors to validate the proposed questionnaire for data collection.

The questionnaire was validated by the following mathematics instructors: Dr. Lucia Basco, Dr. Thelma Yalung, and Ms. Anne Canlyn Manlutac, who suggested adding more questions for each learning modality to get more consistent and reliable data from the respondents.

Furthermore, to establish the reliability of the survey questionnaire, the researcher conducted a pilot test with respondents who were not part of the sample data. Prior to the pilot testing of the questionnaires to assess their reliability in terms of consistency, a letter of endorsement must be secured from the Office of the Schools Division Superintendent.

For the reliability test of the survey questionnaire, Bataan Statistical & Research Consultancy conducted a Cronbach's alpha test, which the questionnaire passed with a score of 0.771.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The gathered data were statistically analyzed using the appropriate tools, with the assistance of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) for Windows version 25.

In describing the dominant mathematics learning styles of the students, frequency, percentage, and mean were used. Moreover, to evaluate the students' preferred learning modalities in Mathematics in the new normal in terms of face-to-face classes, online classes, and blended learning, mean and standard deviation were used.

One-way ANOVA was utilized to determine the significant difference of the students' preferred learning modalities when they are grouped according to learning style.

The computed data was compared to a 0.05 level of significance. Computed data with less than or equal to 0.05 significance level were interpreted as significant, while those greater than 0.05 were interpreted as not significant.

Furthermore, multiple regression was used to develop a path analysis to determine the relationship between students' learning styles, their preferred learning modalities, and their academic performance in Mathematics.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following tables shows the results of the survey regarding the students' learning styles and their preferred learning modalities of the five selected private schools in Dinalupihan, Bataan.

Table 2. Students' Learning Styles in Mathematics

Mathematics Learning Style	f	Percentage
Visual	153	65.67%
Auditory	34	14.59%
Kinesthetic	46	19.74%
Total	233	100%

The table shows that 153, or 65.67%, of the students are visual learners, 46, or 19.74%, are kinesthetic learners, and 34, or 14.59%, are auditory learners. Thus, most students learn mathematics visually because visual representations significantly enhance their understanding. This is because math is not just about understanding the concept of formulas and numbers; it is a process of logical steps and patterns that can be much clearer when they are represented thoroughly.

Table 3. Students' Preferred Learning Modalities in the New Normal in terms of Face-to-Face Class

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. I understand better the delivery of lessons in Mathematics during face-to-face classes.	4.58	0.72	Strongly Agree
2. I improve my mathematical skills through in-person interactions.	4.32	0.79	Strongly Agree
3. I prefer communicating my concerns or questions about the lessons in Mathematics to my teacher in the classroom.	4.19	0.87	Agree
4. I enjoy participating in the discussion in Mathematics during face-to-face classes.	4.15	0.85	Agree
5. I like doing my activities and tasks onsite in Mathematics cooperatively.	4.10	0.82	Agree
6. I prefer to take my assessments (activities, quizzes, and major exams) in the classroom.	4.02	0.89	Agree
Composite Mean	4.23	0.82	Strongly Agree

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 Strongly Agree; 3.40 – 4.19 Agree; 2.60 – 3.39 Neutral; 1.80 – 2.59 Disagree; 1.00 – 1.79 Strongly Disagree

As shown in the table, students' perception of utilized learning modalities in terms of face-to-face class (mean = 4.23, sd = 0.82) was generally "strongly agree." Indicator 1 (mean = 4.58, sd = 0.72) has the highest mean, which may suggest that the student mostly understands the mathematics lessons and performs better during face-to-face classes. However, the lowest mean was on indicator 6 (mean = 4.02, sd = 0.89). This means that the student's preference to take their assessment face-to-face was least observed.

The results strongly indicate that face-to-face instruction is a highly effective modality for teaching and learning mathematics. In a traditional classroom setting, students benefit from direct interaction with their teachers, which allows for immediate clarification of concepts, personalized guidance, and timely feedback on their progress. This real-time communication fosters a dynamic learning environment where misconceptions can be promptly addressed and learning can be tailored to suit individual student needs. Additionally, face-to-face classes facilitate collaborative learning through

group discussions, peer activities, and cooperative problem-solving, all of which contribute to a deeper understanding of mathematical principles. The physical presence of a teacher also plays a motivational role, encouraging active participation and sustained focus among students. These factors combined not only enhance students' comprehension of mathematical topics but also contribute significantly to improved academic performance, increased confidence in handling mathematical problems, and a more positive attitude toward the subject as a whole. Therefore, the findings underscore the value of maintaining in-person mathematics instruction as a key component of effective educational practice.

Table 4. Students' Preferred Learning Modalities in the New Normal in terms of Online Class

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. I understand better the delivery of lessons in Mathematics during face-to-face classes.	2.30	0.84	Disagree
2. I improve my mathematical skills through in-person interactions.	2.39	0.88	Disagree
3. I prefer communicating my concerns or questions about the lessons in Mathematics to my teacher in the classroom.	2.61	0.97	Neutral
4. I enjoy participating in the discussion in Mathematics during face-to-face classes.	2.51	0.90	Disagree
5. I like doing my activities and tasks onsite in Mathematics cooperatively.	2.80	0.97	Neutral
6. I prefer to take my assessments (activities, quizzes, and major exams) in the classroom.	2.89	1.07	Neutral
Composite Mean	2.58	0.94	Disagree

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 Strongly Agree; 3.40 – 4.19 Agree; 2.60 – 3.39 Neutral; 1.80 – 2.59 Disagree; 1.00 – 1.79 Strongly Disagree

As could be gleaned in the table, in terms of an online class (mean = 2.58, sd = 0.94), respondents generally "disagree" with utilizing the online class as a learning modality. The highest is on indicator 6 (mean = 2.58, sd = 1.07), which indicates that the student's preference to take their assessments through online platforms was most likely observed. On the other hand, the lowest mean is on indicator 1 (mean = 2.30, sd = 0.84). This shows that the students are having difficulties understanding the delivery of mathematics lessons through online classes.

The data reveals that students are struggling to cope with how Mathematics lessons are delivered in an online learning modality. Several factors contribute to this difficulty, including limited access to stable internet connection, lack of face-to-face interaction, and challenges in understanding abstract mathematical concepts. Additionally, the data highlights a concerning trend: students have minimal interaction with their teachers during class discussions. This lack of engagement not only hinders

their ability to ask questions and clarify doubts in real-time but also negatively impacts their overall performance and achievement in the subject. The absence of immediate feedback and support reduces their motivation and confidence, making it even harder for them to grasp complex mathematical ideas.

Table 5. Students' Preferred Learning Modalities in the New Normal in terms of Blended Learning

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. I understand better the delivery of lessons in Mathematics both face-to-face and online classes	3.68	0.83	Agree
2. I improve my mathematical skills through in-person interactions, and online platforms and materials.	3.64	0.86	Agree
3. I prefer communicating my concerns or questions about the lessons in Mathematics to my teacher onsite and online classes.	3.56	0.89	Agree
4. I enjoy participating in the discussion in Mathematics onsite and online classes.	3.55	0.83	Agree
5. I like doing my activities and tasks both onsite and online in Mathematics cooperatively.	3.58	0.88	Agree
6. I prefer to take my assessments (activities, quizzes, and major exams) either onsite or online platform.	3.77	0.91	Agree
Composite Mean	3.63	0.87	Agree

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 Strongly Agree; 3.40 – 4.19 Agree; 2.60 – 3.39 Neutral; 1.80 – 2.59 Disagree; 1.00 – 1.79 Strongly Disagree

As shown in the table, students' perception of utilized learning modalities in terms of blended learning (mean = 3.63, sd = 0.87) was generally "agree." Indicator 6 (mean = 3.77, sd = 0.91) has the highest mean, indicating that the student mostly preferred to take their assessment, such as activities, quizzes, and major exams onsite or through online platforms. However, the lowest mean was on indicator 4 (mean = 3.55, sd = 0.83). This shows that the activeness of the students in participating in the class discussion in Mathematics either onsite or through online platforms was least observed.

The findings indicate that the blended learning approach plays a crucial role in influencing students' effectiveness in learning mathematics during the new normal. As educational systems adjust to post-pandemic conditions, this hybrid approach, which combines online and face-to-face class, arises as a pragmatic and strategic solution to persistent issues. It addresses students' diverse learning needs by providing flexibility in time and location, while also ensuring that instructional quality is upheld. Blended learning makes it possible for students to access resources digitally and engage in interactive classroom sessions, creating a balanced and enriched learning experience. In the context of mathematics, where continuous practice and teacher feedback are vital, this modality

offers the opportunity for deeper understanding and improved academic performance. Overall, it serves as a bridge between traditional education and modern technological advancements, promoting resilience and innovation in the learning process.

Table 6. Summary of the Students' Preferred Learning Modalities in the New Normal

Preferred Learning Modalities in the New Normal	Mean	SD	Description
Face-to-Face	4.23	0.82	Strongly Agree
Online Class	2.58	0.94	Disagree
Blended Learning	3.63	0.87	Agree
Composite Mean	3.48	0.88	Agree

As shown in the table, students "agree" on the utilized learning modalities in the new normal (mean = 3.48, sd = 0.88). It can also be observed that the most likely way to deliver lessons in mathematics is through face-to-face classes, while the least observed is through online classes.

The findings suggest that face-to-face classes play a crucial role in enhancing students' understanding of mathematical concepts. This method provides immediate access to the teacher for clarification, allows students to ask questions on the spot, and promotes a more interactive and dynamic classroom environment. Students are able to engage directly with both the teacher and their peers, which fosters a collaborative learning atmosphere that can deepen comprehension and retention of material. On the other hand, distance learning presents several challenges that can hinder students' ability to understand complex mathematical concepts fully. In a remote learning setting, students may struggle with the lack of real-time interaction with their instructor, making it more challenging to clarify misunderstandings or ask questions when they arise. Without the physical presence of a teacher to guide them through difficult topics, students may also feel less motivated and more isolated. Additionally, the distractions of studying from home, such as environmental factors or technological issues, can further contribute to a lack of focus and engagement, leading to poorer comprehension. This contrast highlights the importance of face-to-face instruction in subjects like mathematics, where understanding foundational concepts is critical to future learning. While distance learning offers flexibility, it is evident from these results that onsite classes provide a more structured and supportive learning environment, allowing students to develop a stronger grasp of the material and achieve higher academic performance.

Moreover, the recent study supplements and builds upon the findings of Foo et al. (2021) which indicated that students participating in distance learning exhibited significantly lower performance compared to their peers in traditional face-to-face classrooms. The research highlights that, while distance learning offers flexibility and

convenience, it may not provide the same level of academic engagement or support as in-person learning environments. In addition to the lower overall academic performance, the recent study further observed that students engaged in remote learning tend to struggle in several critical areas. These include a noticeable decline in engagement, where students show reduced participation in class activities, as well as interaction, which is vital for collaboration and the development of communication skills. Furthermore, remote learners were found to have lower levels of preparation, possibly due to the lack of structured schedules and face-to-face accountability.

Table 7. Students' Academic Performance in Mathematics in terms of GPA

GPA	f	Percentage
90 – 100	145	62.23%
85 – 89	66	28.33%
80 – 84	18	7.73%
75 – 79	4	1.72%
Mean	90.45	Outstanding

The table shows that 145 or 62.23% of the respondents had GPAs from 90 to 100, and 66 or 28.33% had it at 85 to 99. At the same time, 18 or 7.73%, had averages from 80 to 84, while 4 or 1.72% had it at 75 to 79. The average GPA of the students is 90.45, which means that their academic performance in mathematics is outstanding.

Results indicate that although the students have not yet fully adapted to the transitions between the different learning modalities their teachers used to deliver mathematics lessons in the new normal, they still manage to cope with the lessons and perform well in mathematics. The shift to various forms of learning, such as online classes, blended learning, and face-to-face sessions, has posed significant challenges for both students and educators. Many students initially struggled with the technological requirements and the adjustments in teaching methods. Despite these challenges, the students demonstrated remarkable resilience and adaptability, finding ways to engage with the material. They have utilized resources such as digital tools, peer support, and self-directed learning strategies to bridge any gaps. As a result, even though they have not fully mastered the new learning approaches, their ability to perform well in mathematics highlights their determination and the effectiveness of their teachers' efforts to support them through this period of transition.

Table 8. Difference Between Students' Preferred Learning Modalities in the New Normal in terms of Face-to-Face Class

Math Learning Style	Mean	SD	F	Sig	Interpretation
Visual	4.29	0.47	3.323	0.038	Significant
Auditory	4.14	0.52			

Kinesthetic 4.09 0.57

At 0.05 level of significance

The table shows a significant difference between the student's learning styles and preferred learning modalities in the new normal regarding face-to-face classes ($F = 3.323$, $p = 0.038$). A LSD post hoc test revealed a significant difference in the preferred learning modality between visual learners (mean = 4.29) and kinesthetic learners (mean = 4.09) with a p-value of 0.021. The results indicate that visual learners typically grasp mathematical concepts more effectively through visual representations, such as diagrams, graphs, and charts, as these methods allow them to make connections between abstract ideas and tangible images. However, kinesthetic learners who thrive on hands-on, physical interaction with learning materials may struggle when attempting to understand abstract mathematical concepts. Their preference for tactile, experiential learning often leads them to engage with physical models or activities, which can be less effective in the context of mathematics, where much of the learning involves theoretical or symbolic understanding that cannot always be easily manipulated or physically demonstrated.

In support of the findings, Krishnan's (2016) study shows that the students' preference is for face-to-face classes. Specifically, the students are more at ease when interacting with their peers and the teachers in face-to-face classes, which helps them to understand and learn mathematics concepts better. Nevertheless, it is in direct opposition to the research conducted by Bordeos et al. (2022), which demonstrated that students encountered obstacles such as a transition phase, insufficient instructional time and interaction, and difficulty understanding the concepts and activities as a result of the limited number of face-to-face classes.

Table 9. Difference Between Students' Preferred Learning Modalities in the New Normal in terms of Online Class

Math Learning Style	Mean	SD	F	Sig	Interpretation
Visual	2.51	0.59			
Auditory	2.67	0.64	3.323	0.041	Significant
Kinesthetic	2.76	0.67			

At 0.05 level of significance

As could be gleaned from the table, there is a significant difference between the student's learning styles and preferred learning modalities in the new normal regarding online classes ($F = 3.233$, $p = 0.041$). A LSD post hoc test reveals that there is a significant difference between the preferred learning modality of visual learners (mean = 2.51) and kinesthetic learners (mean = 2.76) with a p-value of 0.041. Though online classes, facilitated by teachers, were mainly based on visual methods, using charts, diagrams, and other visual tools to explain and discuss the concepts, kinesthetic learners tend to

have a better understanding in online math classes because they thrive on active engagement and hands-on activities. They learn best by doing, so interactive elements like solving problems, using virtual manipulatives, or writing down the computation help them reinforce concepts. This active involvement creates stronger neural connections to the material, while visual learners, who prefer observing images or videos, may struggle without the tactile experience.

The results were reinforced by the findings of Ariawan (2022), who pointed out the negative impacts of online classes as the students experience them. The academic impacts most experienced by students consist of the complexity of mathematics materials, uncertainty regarding the reliability of classmates' grades, decreased motivation for learning, and the belief that their academic performance could have been more optimal. In addition, it is related to the study of Videla et al. (2022), where they found a relationship between teachers' technical knowledge, years of experience, and the types of teaching techniques they employ in online education. Similarly, gaps were discovered between rural and urban schools in terms of instructional styles and educational resources.

Table 10. Difference Between Students' Preferred Learning Modalities in the New Normal in terms of Blended Learning

Math Learning Style	Mean	SD	F	Sig	Interpretation
Visual	3.59	0.66			
Auditory	3.52	0.52	3.203	0.042	Significant
Kinesthetic	3.85	0.74			

At 0.05 level of significance

The table presents that there is a significant difference between the student's learning styles and preferred learning modalities in the new normal regarding blended learning ($F = 3.203$, $p = 0.042$). A LSD post hoc test reveals that there is a significant difference between the preferred learning modality of kinesthetic (mean = 3.85) and visual learners (mean = 3.59) with a p-value of 0.022. It also shows a significant difference between the preferred learning modality of kinesthetic (mean = 3.85) and auditory learners (mean = 3.52) with a p-value of 0.032. This suggests that kinesthetic learners may have an advantage over visual and auditory learners in blended learning modality. This can be attributed to the fact that kinesthetic learner, who learn best through hands-on experiences, are able to apply what they see and learn by physically engaging with the materials and instructions provided by their teachers. This active involvement helps solidify their understanding of concepts, as it enables them to connect the ideas with practice. In contrast, auditory learners rely more on listening and verbal instruction, which may not be as effective in environments that demand practical application. Therefore, kinesthetic learners may perform better in subjects or tasks where direct interaction with the material is essential for mastering the content.

Furthermore, the result of the study is supported by Bidder et al. (2016) through the utilization of blended learning; it improves the integration of online and onsite discussions, including the opportunity to ask questions throughout the course, the quality of communication with peers, and a sense of connection among students in the course. This also strengthens the study of Sessoms (2016), where he found out combining face-to-face and computer-based learning will complement the strengths and weaknesses of the two approaches.

Figure 1. Path Analysis of the Students' Learning Styles, Preferred Learning Modalities, and Their Academic Performance in Mathematics (GPA)

Multiple regression analysis was conducted to establish a path analysis that examines the relationship between students' learning styles, their perceptions of the learning modalities they utilize, and their academic performance in mathematics.

Two distinct models were developed as part of the analysis. The first model focused on the regression relationship between the students' individual learning styles and their preferred learning modalities in the new normal education, which refers to the ongoing adaptations and transitions of the different teaching-learning platforms in the post-pandemic situation. This model sought to identify how students' unique learning preferences align with the learning modalities they gravitate towards in this new educational paradigm.

The second model was developed to analyze the linear relationship between the students' preferred learning modalities in mathematics and their academic performance, as measured by their grade point average (GPA). This model aims to assess the impact

of different learning modalities, such as face-to-face classes, online classes, and blended learning on students' ability to succeed in mathematics. By evaluating the connection between these learning preferences and academic outcomes, the model clearly explains how specific learning modalities contribute to overall student performance in mathematics.

With the use of path analysis, it illustrates the significant effects of the independent variable, which is students' learning styles, and the intermediate variable, which is the preferred learning modalities in the new normal such as face-to-face classes, online classes and blended learning, to the dependent variable which is the grade point average in mathematics.

Table 11. Interpretation of Path Analysis of Student's Learning Styles, Preferred Learning Modalities, and Academic Performance in Mathematics (GPA)

Structural Path	Coefficient	E-value
Direct Effect		
LS → F2F	-0.164	0.906
LS → OC	0.164	
LS → BL	0.131	
LS → GPA	-0.142	0.725
F2F → GPA	0.174	
OC → GPA	-0.209	
BL → GPA	0.119	
Indirect Effect		
LS → F2F → GPA	-0.029	0.816
LS → OC → GPA	-0.034	
LS → BL → GPA	0.016	

The path analysis results revealed that there is a significant relationship between the students' profile and their preferred learning modalities towards their academic performance in Mathematics. Data indicates that the highest direct path is between the students' preferred learning modality in face-to-face classes and their GPA ($\beta = 0.174$), which positively influences the academic performance of the students in mathematics in a face-to-face class. Since face-to-face classes provide a structured, physical classroom environment, they inherently offer many opportunities for direct engagement between students and teachers. This face-to-face interaction facilitates real-time communication, where students can ask questions and receive immediate feedback, which can be critical for reinforcing understanding. Moreover, the dynamic nature of onsite instruction allows for a variety of teaching methods, from traditional lectures to hands-on activities, group discussions, and interactive demonstrations, all of which cater to different learning preferences, such as auditory, visual, and kinesthetic learning styles. The variety in

teaching methods helps to create a more engaging and personalized learning experience, ensuring that students are more likely to grasp complex concepts. However, the overall effectiveness of face-to-face learning still largely depends on how well educators adapt their teaching strategies to meet the diverse needs of their students. A teacher who recognizes the different learning styles within the classroom can adjust their approach accordingly, incorporating a mix of visual aids, interactive exercises, and direct communication to create a more inclusive and supportive environment. When these factors are taken into account, face-to-face learning can significantly enhance students' ability to absorb, process, and retain information.

Meanwhile, the data showed that the highest indirect path is between the students' learning styles and their GPA through blended learning ($\beta = 0.016$), which also positively influences the GPA of the students. This shows that students in the blended learning modality tend to perform better academically than those in other learning modalities in the new normal. This can be attributed to the characteristics of blended learning, which combines both face-to-face classes and online learning opportunities. It offers flexibility, allowing students to access content anytime and anywhere while benefiting from face-to-face classes. Moreover, the blended learning modality fosters a balanced approach to education that effectively combines the strengths of both digital and traditional learning methods. By integrating online resources and face-to-face interactions, this approach offers students the flexibility to learn at their own pace while also benefiting from direct guidance and support from educators. Thus, the result is a dynamic and engaging learning environment that adapts to the diverse needs of students, empowering them with the tools and skills required to succeed academically.

Based on the path analysis, a differentiated instructional model was developed, aligned with the Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, and Evaluation (ADDIE) model from Florida State University. The created model consisted of the following elements: Identify, Design, Implement, and Assess (IDIA).

Figure 2. Differentiated Instruction Model Based on the Path Analysis

In planning a differentiated instruction, the teacher should consider the following:

Identify. Identifying the learning styles of the students by using a standardized learning style inventory, and determine the type of learning modality the teacher will use in delivering instruction. By recognizing the students' learning styles, the teacher may come to a teaching strategy and select the appropriate learning modality for instruction. Moreover, aligning the teaching approach and methods with the students' preferred learning styles, teachers can create a more engaging and effective learning environment that caters to the diverse needs of the class, ensuring that each student is supported in a way that maximizes their learning potential.

Design. Designing instruction that caters to students' individual learning needs is essential in creating an inclusive and effective learning environment. It's important to recognize that each student has a unique learning style, whether it's visual, auditory, kinesthetic, or a combination of these, and tailoring instruction accordingly can significantly enhance their understanding and engagement. By incorporating a variety of lesson content such as multimedia resources, hands-on activities, discussions, and interactive tools teachers can accommodate to different learning preferences and provide opportunities for students to engage with the material in ways that best suit their strengths. This approach not only fosters a deeper understanding of the subject matter but also encourages active participation, critical thinking, and a more personalized learning experience.

Implement. Implementing a well-designed instructional plan is essential in assessing both the effectiveness of the teaching methods and the learning modality. By carefully executing the instructional strategy, teachers can evaluate how effectively they are delivering content to students and whether the materials and methods used align with the students' needs and learning styles.

Assess. Assessing students' learning is crucial for tracking their progress in educational achievement as it provides valuable insights in their understanding, skills, and areas that may need further development. Likewise, assessments help identify gaps in students' knowledge, enabling timely interventions to support their growth. Additionally, through assessment, teachers can evaluate the effectiveness of their teaching methods and make data-driven decisions to improve instructional strategies. Thus, assessment plays a central role in ensuring that students are on track to meet the learning objectives and achieve educational success. It fosters a continuous cycle of improvement, benefiting both teachers and students as they work together to improve the learning experience.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

Most respondents from the selected private schools in Dinalupihan, Bataan S.Y. 2022 – 2023, are visual learners. This is attributed to the fact that the most effective way to learn mathematics is through visual methods, as students are able to understand

abstract concepts and recognize patterns and relationships through charts, diagrams, and other visual representations.

The most preferred learning modality of the students is face-to-face classes. It can also be observed that the students are most likely engage in learning if their lessons are delivered thru onsite classes, while the least observed is through online classes. Results revealed that face-to-face classes create a more interactive, focused, and supportive environment that enhances learning, social development, and overall academic success compared to other learning modalities.

The average grade of the students in their mathematics class is 90.45, which indicates that their achievement is outstanding. The transitions between blended learning, online classes, and face-to-face classes have presented challenges for both students and teachers, but they have shown remarkable adaptability and resilience in overcoming these challenges.

Based on results, data reveals that there is a significant difference between the students' preferred learning modalities when they are classified by learning style. Findings show that the transition between the three primary learning modalities such as face-to-face, online, and blended learning in the new normal have a significant impact on students' performance in Mathematics. The transition introduces various challenges and opportunities, potentially influencing how effectively students engage with and understand mathematical concepts. Factors such as access to technology, teacher-student interaction, and the adaptability of instructional methods could play key roles in determining students' overall success in this subject. Moreover, the effectiveness of these modalities varies based on factors like access to resources and teacher preparedness.

Path analysis is used to model the relationships between the students' learning styles, preferred learning modalities, and their academic performance in mathematics. The data reveals that learning styles and learning modalities can influence academic performance of the students in mathematics. Academic success is shaped by a dynamic combination of individual differences, learning environment, and the alignment of teaching methods and strategies to cater the educational needs of the students. Thus, understanding how students learn best can help them to understand and grasp the lessons effectively.

The first phase involves identifying the students' learning styles and determining the appropriate learning modality for delivering instruction. The second phase is to design differentiated instruction that aligns with the students' learning styles to meet their learning needs. The third phase is to implement the well-planned instruction during the lesson. Lastly, the fourth phase is to assess the students to track their progress and evaluate the effectiveness of the designed instruction.

Recommendations

In the light of the findings and conclusion of this study, the following recommendations are hereby proposed:

1. To improve student achievement and engagement, teachers incorporate diverse teaching methods and provide individualized instruction based on students' learning styles. For instance, visual learners are given more concrete examples and visual representations in the discussion; auditory learners are provided with recorded discussions, and kinesthetic learners engage in various activities and tasks.
2. Educational institutions may encourage and support the integration of digital platforms such as live demonstrations media, interactive assessment and digital portfolio systems to enhance and provide different assessment forms.
3. In a distance learning modality, parents need to collaborate with the teachers to assist and guide their children who are facing challenges in the transition of the different learning modalities in the new normal to monitor and track the performance of their children.
4. To broaden the knowledge and skills of teachers in a distance learning modality, educational institutions may provide opportunities for their teachers to attend seminars, trainings, and workshops.
5. It is suggested that teachers are advised to implement a multimodal teaching approach that integrates into different learning styles into their mode of instructions to enhance the students' interest and motivation.
6. The Identify, Design, Implement, and Assess (IDIA) model may help teachers in designing and planning differentiated instruction. Teachers must recognize students' learning styles, determine the appropriate mode of instruction, incorporate diverse instructional materials aligned with students' learning styles, and provide different activities that cater to their educational needs.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In conducting this study, the researcher ensured compliance with established ethical standards in research:

The researcher sought approval from the Dean of Instruction of the Graduate School of Bataan Peninsula State University to survey the study from the selected private schools in Dinalupihan, Bataan. Upon approval, the researcher will seek approval from the Office of the Schools Division Bataan Superintendent to conduct a pilot and actual survey for the study. After issuing the letter from the SDO Bataan, the researchers also sought permission from the school principals of the selected schools. Upon approval of the request letter to conduct the study, the researcher coordinated with the mathematics

teachers in the selected schools to systematically administer the survey questionnaires and provide the consent letter to the potential respondents.

In administering the data collection, the researcher explained the directions before the respondents answer the given questionnaires. The researcher also guided the students as they complete the questionnaire and address any questions they may have. Students were assured that their response would remain confidential between the respondents and the researcher.

After the respondents finished answering the questionnaire, the researcher retrieved the survey and the consent letter. The collected data will be kept and stored in a secured storage.

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